

Changing Business Landscape: A Study on Reshaping a Future-New World of Work

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ABSTRACT

The workforce of today is facing unprecedented transformations in the nature of work. As a result of the changing business landscape, the employees are expected to adapt to the new work methods at a rapid pace. Furthermore, the transition to the desired future, has been accelerated by various factors. At present, the pandemic has forced businesses to invest in advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, robotics, cloud computing, and data analytics.

Consequently, there has been an imperative shift in the adoption of technology, in every sector, across the globe to suit the culture of remote working. While the employees are stepping into this new-age technology, acquiring skills to work in collaboration with the advanced machines forms an intrinsic part of the organizations' overall improvement. With the advent of pandemic, there have been massive skill-shifts. When the employees look ahead, there is an evident change in their perception of up-skilling and reskilling – a valued opportunity to a crucial step in remaining employable. In an era of constant changes; continuous learning, redeployment and redefinition will form an integral part of the new workplace. This study thereby, aims to identify the significant causes for the major transitions in the workforce and the essential skills required to thrive in the future. The study is qualitative in nature and secondary data was used, to gather multiple perspectives of the executives and researchers. The tools that were used for the study comprises QDA Miner, Excel, Affinity Diagram, Fishbone diagram, and Tableau. The tools were employed to code the keywords, organize the data based on the objectives and draw inferences post a thorough analysis. Tableau was used to interpret the data in a visual format. The outcome was aimed at identifying the four forces of changing work environment -technology, pandemic, mind-set shift of the workforce and emerging practices. In addition, the most in-demand “hard” and “soft” skills for the future world of work, were analysed and interpreted using Tableau. Subsequently, the outcome places a premium on the importance of soft skills due to technological dominance. This implies that human talent is an integral part of the work environment but only when the qualities such as empathy, leadership, communication, agility and the like are acquired.

Keywords: Skills for future, Workplace changes, Technological impact , Millennials at workplace,

I. INTRODUCTION

The workforce and technology are becoming more global, digital, and technology-focused in congruence with the ever-changing business requirements. However, this isn't the first time that the society is experiencing change in its cultural idea of work. The pre-industrial economy experienced the craftsmanship style of work in which the craftsman was responsible for end-to-end transmission of goods and services. The industrial revolution has replaced the concept of craftsmanship, with the usage of machines for repetitive tasks. Gradually, a multitude of changes began to redefine the work. In the current era, technology is shaping new work methods, paving the way for man-machine collaboration. While the technology pressure was surmounting at a slower pace, COVID-19 has accelerated the pace of digital adoption. This is being tagged as the "New Normal" – to embrace the rapid transition towards a virtual work environment. The transitions include working from home, meeting clients virtually, building networks through digital collaboration tools and many such changes.

Change, transformation, and evolutions are the terms that have become a common parlance in the work economy, especially due to the global pandemic. All the forms of work processes, culture and various other concepts related to the workplace have been transformed lately. The business landscape is undergoing tremendous changes to stay relevant. With the outbreak of COVID-19; there had been massive transformations such as virtual workspace models, intensified technology usage and digital collaboration tools for team gatherings. The subtle element that must be understood here is – as the businesses are embracing changes, the employees are going to be pressurised to travel along the path of transformations. To tackle the situation, the employees must be aware of the causes for the change, which will aid them to identify their areas of potential and invest time and resources corresponding to those areas. This could assist the employees to gain significant knowledge or professional skills to sustain the dynamic business environment. This study has the following specific objectives:

- ✚ To determine the major forces of the transitions in the workplace that have contributed to massive changes.
- ✚ To determine the drivers of the forces and establish relationships between those drivers, to derive the root-cause for the changes.
- ✚ To define the impact of rapid transitions that is existent in the current work environment.
- ✚ To identify the essential skills that are expected of employees to thrive in the changing business landscape.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizations must constantly change to thrive in the volatile business environment. This provides an indication for the employees that their everyday work-lives will undergo transitions as well. Employees might have to face changes in their work-schedule, technology usage, designated procedures and policies or even more significant changes based on their industry requirements. Especially, the nature of work will experience a tremendous shift due to the emerging technologies. These technologies evolving at an unprecedented pace will become an integral part of the future work environment. This will impact various sectors including its stakeholders. The employers will have to retool several prototypes and job processes according to the updates in the trend. Subsequently employees should endure those changes and showcase their adaptability to change. It is only the blend of that will represent the success of reshaping an enterprise.

Transition in the workforce ecosystem

The idea of working in any time and at any place has made the workplace a virtual workspace. In the words of the (Ware & Grantham, 2003) the technology has brought about transitions in the traditional workplace.

As the competition increases, there would be displacement in the current workforce. The adoption of artificial intelligence and automation across various sectors will accompany the need to acquire the appropriate skills. The physical, manual, and basic cognitive skills which sufficed the current industry requirements will be substituted by the demand for higher cognitive skills, social, emotional and digital interaction skills. (Bughin, et al., 2018).

The transformations should be carried out rapidly yet with an exemplary strategic plan that highlights the necessities for the change. Companies should leverage social media learning as a part of their transition to change those aids in a well-informed decision-making process. Learning is integral to any

organization. With a rapid digital growth in work processes, the companies can utilise the social media platform to make the learning more engaging.

Role of millennials in the change

With the baby boomers retiring, there will be a subsequent increase in the population of the millennials. Millennials are tech-savvy and will be able to grasp the key technological tools better than the other generations.

(Gilchrist, 2019) says that the millennials will tend to work with more freelancers, empower remote working processes and cultivate interest in constant reskilling. As technology threatens the traditional work methodology, the millennials will remain accountable to equip their skill sets in congruence with the trend. In addition to which, (Hershatter & Epstein, 2010) states that the millennials are addressed as “Digital Natives” due to their greater affinity with the digital world. The emerging artificial intelligence, automation and robotics will bring out the spirit of motivation in such a workforce.

However, the employers will have to undergo a tough time restructuring the traditional system of management to blend with the interests of the millennial workforce because of their behavioural traits and challenging attitudes.

Technological influence in different sectors

Technology has gained a pre-eminent position in the current industrial revolution. The generation and interpretation of the accurate data is necessary to predict the customer demands and focus on their behaviour post outcome. The technological tools such as BI, cloud and data analytics are mainly designed to accelerate the process. Technology has added credibility to results by making the whole process data driven thereby displacing the manual work at a minimal level. (Attaran, et al., 2019)

(Nazeemudeen, et al., 2020) compiled the benefits of blockchain as Patient related benefits and organisational related benefits ,Apart from the benefits that it could provide, there are certain disadvantages that have to be encountered in the usage. While the transactions could be made online, there is a limit to the number of executions that can happen at once, giving rise to the scalability issues. The organizations must devise methods for the trade-off between the transaction volume and the system power required to handle the transactions simultaneously. In addition, the maintenance of the integrated supply chain demands expertise in the IT and essential technical skills. Also,the installation cost of incorporating blockchain in the hospitals is high in the initial stages.(Nazeemudeen, et al., 2020)

Various sectors including **banking and insurance, energy and mining, healthcare, manufacturing, and retail** will have to rework on their corporate structure including their work approaches to harness the potent effect of the tech and sustain labour. This is because automation is considered to have a significant potential in the future.

Skill gap

Skill being the most important phenomena of the human capital, must be constantly updated in accordance with the changing industry requirements. With an exponential growth in utilization of technology, the development of skills for its interaction remains detrimental amongst the current workforces. This condition indicates “*Skill Gap*” which is normally due to the lack of skills necessary or skill mismatch that arises due to the gap between the labour demand and supply. Furthermore, (S, et al., 2019) says that it could lead to incompetence and affect the performance of the employees which in turn lowers the organizational efficiency.

(Sharma, 2019) states that the organization must ensure that the workforce stays relevant and optimistic to handle new era of innovation and efficiency. Also, there lies a responsibility of the organizations to identify the wider gaps and bring new knowledge for a better relevance.

World Economic Forum (2025). The Future of Jobs Report indicates that 86% of employers expect AI and information processing technologies to transform their businesses by 2030, with a significant focus on reskilling and upskilling strategies.

Bone, M., Ehlinger, E., & Stephany, F. (2023) this study finds a shift towards skill-based hiring, especially in AI and green sectors, with a decline in the emphasis on formal degrees.

On analysing the reviewed literatures, the key factor highlighted is the prevalent “Skill Gap” that is to be addressed sooner. Also, there is an evident emphasis laid on re-imaging the workforce development plans and readjustment of the existing skill sets. The major contributor to this circumstance is the

evolving technology and the unexpected pandemic. Organizations have to remain proactive in their responses to the current transition. The technology will automate and augment the current nature of the work. However, the intertwine of humans and machines are expected to generate new work activities and employment opportunities. As technology backs the technical activities related to a particular job or sector, the manual labour will have to route their career enhancements in developing the advanced digital interaction skills for the human-machine interaction and people management skills that is far off from being replaceable.

This study thereby, aims to analyse and report the role of undermined metrics such as - the emerging work practices, mind-set shift, futuristic skills and the hybrid working models that are equally responsible for the recreation of the working ecosystem.

RESEARCH GAP

Upon reviewing the literature, the powerful synergy that tends to exist between the humans and machines is vividly identified. The organizations are introducing advanced system processors in the workplace to improve accuracy and speed, thereby exhibiting readiness for a dynamic environment. As a result, the employees have started to gain awareness regarding the impact of technologies on their jobs. In addition, it is also important for the workforce to understand various other factors that are set to shape their future towards a major transition. This would help them prioritise their activities accordingly and in turn sustain the rapid transitions. This study thereby, aims to analyse and report the role of undermined metrics such as - the emerging work practices, mind-set shift, futuristic skills and the hybrid working models that are equally responsible for the recreation of the working ecosystem.

III.METHODS

For the present study, secondary data was taken from journal papers, white papers, interview transcripts, reports, and book sections. QDA Miner was used to code the data as per the defined variables. QDA miner can be used to segregate categories of the data and code the records as per those categories. The data specific to the desired codes could be retrieved by the various retrieval options available in the software. (Keyword, section, code, frequency). Excel was used to clean the unstructured data and organize the data as per the needs. Affinity diagram was used to gauge multiple perspectives of the executives, researchers; and group those into four forces of change to derive an organized set of data. This set of data is used for the root cause analysis which is done using the Fishbone diagram. Finally, CE is used to identify the potential causes for the changing workplace that is having a major impact on the employees. This is done in-order to determine countermeasures to thrive in the future work environment. The current study follows a theoretical sampling method which assists the researcher to formulate categories, discover elements that fit in those categories and depict the corresponding interrelationship between the categories. The theoretical sampling is systematically and constantly applied to generate an updated or new context of the topic under study.

The following steps were followed during data collection: -

Table 0-1 Steps involved in data collection

Identification of records	Google scholar, Elsevier, JSTOR, Research gate, Springer World Economic Forum, McKinsey reports, Reports by Deloitte, Accenture, PwC
Keywords/Phrases used for search	Skills for future, Workplace changes, Technological impact on the workforce, Millennials at workplace, Workforce Demographics, Reshaping workforce, Emerging HR practices, HR Analytics, data-driven HR
Screening	Records were screened based on title and abstract relevant to the future world of work
Assessing full-text articles	Records were constantly updated by comparing the data with references from research journals, and outcomes of the survey obtained from reports published by well-established organizations to ensure validity

Source: Self-compiled

The records that remained, after the aforementioned steps have been performed is used for analysis.

Identification of factors causing changes

1.1.1 Coding data

All the possible causes as identified in the records are assigned with the codes formulated by the researcher. The coded data is then retrieved in a coding table and exported to Excel for further analysis. The screenshot of the coding console is as shown in the figure 3-1.

Figure 0-1 Representation of analysis by coding

Source: Self-

generated using QDA Miner

1.1.2 Data analysis using Excel

The exported data is then analysed to formulate keywords related to the changing workplace. This is done to ease the broad categorisation of the data. In the analysis, the keywords related to qualities of the millennials, virtual workplaces, social-distancing measures post pandemic, changes in business strategy, changing culture of the organisation, technological influence, post-pandemic requirements, and the various emerging practices to tackle the changes is formulated. This is done in-order to determine the significant four-best forces of change and the factors attributing to those forces. The formulated keywords are then consolidated to categorise them according to their natural relations.

Figures 3-2 and 3-3 are a visual representation of the aforementioned process described in detail.

Figure 0-2 Excel sheet displaying the analysis of coded data

Text	Codes	Keywords
185 Many organizations are now taking a plunge in creating and implementing flexible work practices	Causes	Flexible work practices
186 Technological advancements hitting the business landscape such as cloud computing, smart	Causes	Technological advancements are utilised
187 Generation Z feel that their best of work performance is not recognized, which in turn demot	Causes	Expect rewards and incentives
188 Generation Z is entrepreneurial and want to make their own identity	Causes	Entrepreneurial mind set
189 The technology-savvy Generation Z living in a wired environment, are habitual to get immedi	Causes	Tech-savvy
190 HR practices should allow a cohesive team environment, where employees socialize, forge m	Causes	
191 Constructive feedback can help employees of Generation Z for being better in their designat	Causes	Expect constructive feedback
192 Generation Z expects that their employers will provide freedom to spend some of their time i	Causes	
193 Generation Z is the generation of volunteers and donors and is eager to contribute to differe	Causes	
194 The Global Trend 2017 report also mentions that Generation Z, unlike their previous cohorts,	Causes	High Social responsibility
195 Considering digital innovation, after the advent of new technology platforms such as virtual	Causes	
196 Technological advancements and gadgets have a significant influence on Generation Z	Causes	High technological influence
197 Gen Z cited positive attitude (42%) and clear targets (37%), while Millennials stated open co	Causes	Require clear targets
198 clear instructions and training on the job	Causes	Systematic
199 providing a checklist	Causes	
200 Facilitate communication	Causes	
201 Use technology such as videos and a variety of communication media to introduce informatio	Causes	Digital collaboration tools are used
202 Reinforce existing culture and sense of purpose	Causes	Sense of purpose
203 set aside a block of uninterrupted time to spend with the newcomer to answer questions and	Causes	
204 The notion of equality is important to Gen Z, with 91% believing that everyone is equal and s	Causes	
205 Gen Z has to rely on their own subjective feelings of justice to decide whether a comment is	Causes	rely on subjective feelings
206 Gen Z is significantly more likely to report their mental health as fair or poor as compared with	Causes	Report mental health as fair or poor
207 Sixty-seven percent of Gen Z in the United States and 85% worldwide say that stress preven	Causes	Easily stressed
208 73% of Gen Zers feel that they could have used more emotional support in the past year.67	Causes	need emotional support
209 Gen Z is unique in growing up with a culture of safety where overpro- tective parenting inad	Causes	Lack life skills
210 Present skills as being learnable and that everyone is learning on the job	Causes	OJT preferred
211 Forty-two percent of Gen Z saw they want their boss to have a positive attitude and 33% w	Causes	

Source: Self-generated

Figure 0-3 Excel sheet displaying the consolidation of the keywords

A	B	C	D
1			Qualities
2 Remote working	Cultural Shifts	Mind-set Shift	need emotional support
3 Virtual meeting	Empathy	Independent contractors	Lack life skills
4 Video communications	Inclusivity	Prefer freelancing	OJT preferred
5 Flexibility	Distributed Workspaces	Lack of loyalty	Digitally communication often
6 Diffused Work-life boundaries	Importance to trust and belongingness	Technology-enabled	Autonomy
7 Virtual collaboration with co-workers	Social footprint	Independent	Adaptable to change
8 Rising hybrid remote-office models	Training	Collaborative	Entitled to perks and promotion
9 Talent sharing across globe	Upskilling Initiatives	Emphasis on incentives and rewards	People oriented
10 Diverse workforce	E-learning models	Growth mindset	Passionate
11 Increased gender equity	Development of future-proof skills	Prefer coaching and mentoring	Expect autonomy
12 Decreased overhead costs	Human skills	Innovative learning techniques preferred	Expect positive feedback
13 Improve employee morale	Technology	Reduced trust	Informal Social media channels for
14 Workforce	Cloud - SaaS applications	Sense of purpose	Transparency prioritised
15 Innovation	Internet of things	Flexible work culture	Respect expertise
16 Creativity	Advanced analytics	timely feedback	Collaborative
17 Adaptive teams	Robotic process Automation	Value training and development	Technology-mediated communication
18 Pressure on employees	Artificial intelligence (AI)	Open-mindedness	screen based communication
19 Proactive teams	Cybervetting	Pragmatic	Diffused work-life boundaries
20 Recruitment of contingent workers	Quantum computing	Inclusivity/Acceptance of diversity	Adaptive
21 Changing employee expectations	Digital collaboration tools	Multi-taskers	Tech savvy
22 Virtual workspaces	Data lakes	Meaningful work	Tech focused
23 Visible employee accountability	Augmented reality	Frequently Job-hop	Emphasis on mentoring
24 Increased job insecurity		Emphasis on financial stability	Multitasking
25 Skeletal staffing		Flexible work practices	Unique set of values
26 Priorities		Technological advancements are utilised	re-inforce kindness
27 Strategic flexibility		Expect rewards and incentives	aim for a flexi timing
28 Digital collaboration tools		Entrepreneurial mind set	job that makes a difference

Source: Self-generated

1.1.3 Affinity diagram

The affinity diagram is used to categorise the drivers of change in a more specific context. The keywords formulated using excel are employed for further categorisation.

Figure 0-4 Affinity diagram depicting four forces of change

Source: Self-generated using ConceptDraw

1.1.4 Fishbone diagram

The cause-and-effect diagram (CE) or the Fishbone diagram (Ishikawa diagram) is employed in this study to analyse the most significant drivers of the changes in the work economy. As per analysis, the affinity diagram assisted the researcher to identify the forces of change and categorise the factors attributing to those changes. The well-organised data is thus used, to intensify the relationship between each sub-drivers with the forces of change that are responsible for the rapid transitions.

Figure 0-5 Fishbone diagram depicting changes in the work environment

Sou

rice: Self-generated using ConceptDraw

The figure 3-5 is generated based on the categorised drivers of change as analysed using the affinity diagram. The figure 3-5 depicts the fishbone analysis that highlights the major causes of the change, the drivers of those factors and the relationship that strengthens the impact of change.

Assessment of the essential skills for the future world of work

1.1.5 Categorisation using QDA Miner

The skills are assigned with the codes “**Hard**”, and “**Soft**” with respect to their types; pertaining to the research. The coded skills are then retrieved and exported to Excel.

Description

The coded data is based on the research papers indicating the important 21st century skills and that of skills-in-demand post pandemic. Apart from that, the multiple perspectives of executives gathered through the survey results of companies like Deloitte, Accenture, PwC and the like, along with the interview transcripts and webinar transcripts obtained from global publications were included in determining the essential skills. Upon identifying the essential skills based on the frequency of its occurrence in the records, it is exported to Tableau for further visualisation.

1.1.6 Data interpretation using tableau

Tableau is employed to visualise and interpret the significant skills for the ever-changing work environment. The data visualisation and analysis is segmented into two –

- ✚ **Classification of essential hard and soft skills (representing the best 10 in each categories)**
- ✚ **Fundamental skills or crucial (must-have) skills that are considered mandatory to thrive in the changing environment –**

IV.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The four forces of change are termed as - *Transitions due to pandemic, Technology, Emerging Practices and Mind-set shift of employees*. The factors attributing to those changes are categorised under the corresponding forces. The factors are mapped to their respective categories based on their relationship with the forces. This is because the forces have emerged stronger due to the presence of certain factors. It is essential to understand the impact of these factors on the organizations, to thrive in the future.

Emerging Practices

Flexibility and autonomy at work are the two terms that employees covet across the globe. Hence, businesses are changing their strategies and structures to create opportunities for mutual gains. At the outset, new practises arise out of those opportunities.

Contingent Worker Expansion

The future is heading towards a hybrid working model that combines the remote working and office timings with a greater flexibility. This provides freedom for workers who will have the option to work from home, office or a centralised hub at a closer distance to their locality. With this, the reduction in cost is facilitated by recruiting contingent workers. The “gig economy” that comprises temporary workers like freelancers and independent contractors are hired to perform assigned roles through the online platform. The future of work though ahead, is expected to consist of a new realm – the hybrid model with a gig economy, thus paving way for a mutual gain.

Customized Employment

Customized employment provides equal opportunity to all the employees to participate in community life. The needs, interests and skills of the employee are determined post which the job content and the working environment are tailor-made through a negotiation process, according to the identified information. While employers cater to the needs of the employees, there is another way through which the customizations take place. The employees tend to utilise any opportunities to tailor their job-based interactions and tasks to foster job satisfaction.

Inclusivity

A productive environment, inclusive of greater diversity acceptance, and mission-driven autonomous teams is allowed to operate. The autonomous teams facilitate complex problem solving, manage client-relationship and formulate strategies.

Mind-set shift of employees

With the demographic transitions and the immediate shifts in the workplace, the employees are having a mind-set shift in the way they work. The main reasons attributing to the mind-set shift are as mentioned-

Flexible Work culture

Employees are experiencing a major trauma due to unprecedented changes in the nature of work. The remote work has diffused their work-life balance and undermined their well-being at certain tough times. Hence, the employees are seeking for a flexible culture with respect to time and location that aids to enhance their productivity.

Digital Exposure

The Generation-Z and millennials entering the job market are tech-savvy who are exposed to social media and digital platforms to a much greater extent, than the rest of the generations. They generally lack emotional support and life skills as they generally have minimal face-to-face interactions. Due to this, they seek social media support and spend a longer screen time.

Impactful qualities

The millennials are socially responsible and thereby they tend to choose jobs that has a sense of purpose or the job that makes a difference. If the millennials find that their jobs no longer interests them, they seek a new job immediately.

Pandemic

Pandemic has been a catalyst to reinvent the future world of work. As new technologies emerge, the employees will be taught a new set of values, behaviours and mind-sets.

Remote Working

The main concern for the business during pandemic was – reduction in cost. As the executives are seeking ways to decrease the overheads, remote working is considered as a permanent solution. Certain reputed companies have declared permanent work-from-home for the employees.

Shifting priorities

As employees are working remotely, they are prone to stress due to lack of motivation and physical movements. This is taking a toll on the health of the employees. Apart from that, employees are anxious as they have to frequently adapt to changes to retain their jobs. Hence, the companies have shifted their priorities by introducing executive pay-cuts to offset employee costs. Also, various employee well-being initiatives are introduced such as establishing hotlines to remain responsive to the queries and concerns of the employees.

Pragmatic solutions

Employers are trying to formulate practical solutions to overcome the crisis. To contain the spread of novel coronavirus, skeletal staffing is employed. The minimum number of employees essential for business operations alone, work from the office. Also, businesses are widely expanding their operations by strengthening their social footprint. The companies leverage social media and technology to resolve societal problems, thereby seeking a mutual gain. To support these measures, pragmatic (realistic) solutions are supposed to be devised for long-term success.

Talent Sharing

Virtual workspaces have given rise to the E-learning models. The companies are engaging their employees through learning and development initiatives. Coursera, edX, and various other e-learning platforms have been utilised to develop the competencies of employees to thrive in the changing business landscape. The flexibility of choosing the duration and timing of the course is based on the convenience of the individuals who enrol in the course.

Technology

Technology has the ability to bring advantages and opportunities for business. The companies can experience a greater accuracy and endurance in the work processes. This is because the decisions can be more objective through the availability of data that can be stored in multitude by the technological devices. Technology can also help companies to create advanced products, innovative services and lessen the time-to-market period that can improve the profitability at a longer run. Moreover, technological products can reduce the cost of operations and increase productivity by performing certain repetitive tasks.

Data based insights

As operations are becoming digitised, there are various ways with which the data can be stored and processed to generate valuable insights for longevity of the businesses. Cloud computing; Software as a Service (SaaS) is a cloud-based method of providing software services to the users. The applications stored in the cloud; can be accessed from any digital devices as the operations pertaining to the applications run on cloud rather than a particular device. It is useful for business to operate efficiently, innovate faster and collaborate with clients instantly.

Man-machine collaboration

Robotic process automation is a technology that allows businesses to configure “robots” to emulate and integrate the human interactions with the digital devices to execute a business process. While RPA is used to perform repetitive tasks and improve accuracy, augmented reality offers an interactive experience of a real-world using digital sound or visual elements. Businesses have leveraged the advantage of augmented reality to provide efficient training to employees to bring about on-the-job feel to the employees. The man-machine collaboration, though synergetic, is set to change the traditional ways and bring about new ways of working in the business landscape.

Cyber-vetting

The employees, these days, have a greater digital exposure through social media and various other digital collaboration tools. The identity of the employees has a greater visibility through the social media profiles that they create, this includes profiles in Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn and the like. The potential recruiters leverage this opportunity to vet people’s online presence and “internet reputation” to discover more about the candidate. The recruiters consider this as an advantage, as this allows them to gauge the potential of the candidate through his/her ideas and comments posted in the social media. Cyber-vetting is thus made possible by the candidate’s presence in social media.

The aforementioned factors indicate the changing work methods that are being adopted by businesses to sustain in the changing landscape.

Description

The categorisation of the skills is based on the description of soft and hard skills. The soft skills are those personal, intangible skills that aid an individual to get along with everyone in the workplace. It is also called “interpersonal skills” or “people skills” which is crucial for professional development. Contrarily, hard skills are the industry knowledge, technical know-how and quantifiable abilities that are required to perform a job or task. **Error! Reference source not found.**

Classification of top 10 hard and soft skills

Description

The data from excel is imported to the Tableau. As the objective aims to classify and visualise the important-10 hard and soft skills for the future, charting is employed. The side-by-side bars is a built-in charting feature that is used for better comparison, by placing the essential hard and soft skills in a parallel structure. This makes it compatible for further analysis.

Figure 0-1 Representation of Top 10 Professional Skills [Technical and Soft skills]

Source:

Self-generated side-by-side bars using Tableau

Interpretation

From the analysis, “Creativity” and “Critical thinking” are at a greater demand compared to the rest of the soft skills. On the other hand, “Digital literacy” and “UX design” are the most sought-after technical skills by the employers. The other skills categorised under the hard-skills category are majorly technology-focused such as – big data and cloud-based analytics. The detailed description of the important skills is explained as follows.

Description of Hard Skills

The essential hard skills that assists the employees in rapid career advancements are described in the table 4-1

Table 0-1 Application of Hard skills

Skills	Application
Affiliate Marketing	The process by which an affiliate (marketer) earns commission for marketing (or) selling another company's products or services. (Adams, 2017)
Artificial Intelligence (AI)	Large amounts of data can be processed and the patterns can be recognised by employing AI. AI relies on natural language processing (NLP) and deep learning to learn from experience, adjust to new inputs and perform tasks like humans. (SAS Insights, n.d.)
Block chain	An open, distributed ledger that records transactions efficiently. Though it is expected to take a longer time for adoption, it eliminates the role of intermediaries like the bankers and lawyers, in the transaction process
Cloud Computing	Cloud computing enables the delivery of computing servers over the internet for faster innovation, economies of scale and flexible resources. The computing services include server, storage, databases, analytics, and intelligence (Microsoft Azure, n.d.)
Coding	Creation of websites, apps and software are made possible through coding. This helps business earn profit by customizing the websites according to the needs of the customer.
Data Analytics	Data analytics includes gathering the necessary data as per business requirements, identifying data sources, cleaning and analysing those to provide insights. Also, the visualisation of the insights and communication of the same forms a major part of the data analytics. (Coursera, n.d.)
Design Thinking	Design thinking can be described as an innovative problem-solving approach that includes understanding the problem, developing possible solutions, testing, refining and implementing those solutions. (Linke, 2017)
Digital literacy	Digital literacy is the basic knowledge of using digital devices, software and the internet to collaborate with others and thereby create information. (Microsoft Digital Literacy, n.d.)
STEM	STEM is the abbreviation of Science, Technology, Engineering and Math, a curriculum designed for the youth of the nation to build their problem solving and decision making skills. (U.S. Department of Education, n.d.)
UX Design	User-experience design, a high demand field has its applicability in a variety of fields. This deals with the creation of compelling screen-based experiences for applications and websites. (Coursera, n.d.)

Source: Self-generated

Description of Soft skills

The essential soft skills for the future are described in the table 4-2

Table 0-2 Application of Soft skills

Skills	Application
Agility	Agility is the ability to discern patterns and their corresponding linkages, and make fresh connections between various patterns or concepts. The pace at which this is performed, determines the capability of the employee to adapt to new circumstances
Collaborative	Collaborative skills are team-oriented skills that aid in getting along with the people in the work to achieve a common goal or a project completion. (Vasanthakumari, 2019)

<i>Communication</i>	Communication is a process by which a message is transmitted from the sender to the receiver. The clarity and appropriateness with which the message is delivered determines the efficiency. The transmission could either be done using verbal context such as writing, reading, e-mail and the like or through nonverbal context such as body language, eye-movements and facial expressions
<i>Creativity</i>	Creativity is the ability to generate and recognise ideas for problem-solving or innovation. It can be used to obtain alternate possible solutions for a problem. (Vasanthakumari, 2019)
<i>Critical thinking</i>	Critical thinking is defined as the ability to employ rational thinking that helps to understand the logical connection between various ideas. (Vasanthakumari, 2019)
<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	Emotional Intelligence refers to the ability of individuals to recognise, use, control and manage one's own emotions, as well as other's emotions. This is done to radiate optimism and control on oneself during crisis or challenging times.
<i>Empathy</i>	Design thinking can be described as an innovative problem-solving approach that includes understanding the problem, developing possible solutions, testing, refining and implementing those solutions.
<i>Entrepreneurial Mind-set</i>	The entrepreneurial mind-set enables the attitude of learn-and-grow by exploiting knowledge, being decisive and assessing failure to improve constantly. It is especially important in the changing business landscape.
<i>Leadership</i>	Leadership is an overarching skill that is described as the ability to influence others, with or without authority that includes presence of good interpersonal skills, self-awareness, conflict management and decision-making. (Vasanthakumari, 2019)
<i>Negotiation</i>	Negotiation is the ability to achieve a mutual gain by discovering each other's interest. It also involves settling the differences between the parties involved, by avoiding dispute and argument. (Vasanthakumari, 2019)

Source: Self-compiled.

Assessing the importance of soft skills

While a blend of “hard” and “soft” skills are equally important to perform a job, executives and researchers have placed a premium on the soft skills. This is evident from the pie-chart presented below.

Figure 0-2 Pie-chart displaying the distribution of important skills

Source:

Self-generated using Tableau

Interpretation

Soft skills are transferable skills that employees can apply in any kind of work that they perform. Also, soft skills are aligned with the general disposition and personality of the candidate. The pie-chart indicates the importance of soft skills. This is because every job role requires at least a minimum level of interactions with the co-workers. In addition, soft skills are more personality-driven and it allows the recruiters to gauge the potential of the candidate to excel in the work environment. Another concern of employers is - productivity. A highly technical person need not necessarily be productive unless he/she has the drive to perform.

1.1.7 Growing importance of soft skills

The findings imply that soft skills (or) professional skills are at a higher demand than the technical skills. The employees are expected to be highly adaptive amidst the unprecedented changes in the workplace economy, and the technological dominance. LinkedIn's list of most in-demand skills is compiled, and the outcome highlights the importance of the soft skills.

Figure 0-3 Comparison of Most-In demand skills [2016-2020]

Source:

Self-generated using Tableau

LinkedIn’s most in-demand skills (global) from the year 2016-2020 is depicted in the figure. There is an increased demand of professional skills like “Creativity”, “Collaboration”, “Communication”, “Adaptability”, “Leadership” and “Time Management”. This points to the fact that the findings of the current study have been congruent to LinkedIn’s Top 10 in-demand skills (global) list. Also, the researcher has stressed the growing importance of soft skills which has also been published in the skill list. While the blend of both hard and soft skills is quint-essential for an employee’s career progression, the soft skills are mandatory to thrive in the future. The present study (perspectives of multiple researchers and executives) indicates a higher congruence with respect to LinkedIn’s most in-demand skills list.

1.1.8 Essential skills for the future

Description

While certain skills help employees progress in their career, there is another set of skills that are considered fundamental to perform any kind of job. The fundamental or crucial skills are charted in the form of tree maps to provide better visualisation of the analysis. Each rectangle is subdivided into smaller rectangles, based on the proportion to the whole. The proportion indicates the frequency of skills mentioned in the records by the researchers and executives. The legend termed as – “frequency”, indicates the pattern with which the data is coloured or proportioned. The tooltip is placed on the “Creativity” skill to highlight the parameters used for analysis. The tree map presented in the figure, is a consolidation of the aforementioned “ten important hard-and-soft skills to be acquired”.

Figure 0-4 Tree Map displaying essential skills to thrive in future

Source:

Self-generated using Tableau

Interpretation

Crucial skills are the mandatory fundamental skills that an employee is expected to have. Apart from the soft skills, “Digital Literacy” is the only hard skill that has maintained its importance in the overall rating of the most essential skills. This is because, majority of the organizations are increasingly adopting the digital platforms, performing digital operations, and communicating through the digital collaboration tools. Hence, the employees are expected to have a fundamental understanding of the digital operations to thrive in the work environment.

Soft skills or human-centric skills are the most crucial. In the constantly changing business landscapes, the ability to cope up with change is the definition for success. From the tree maps, 4 C’s that are quint-essential for the dynamic work environment are deduced.

- ✚ Creativity
- ✚ Critical thinking
- ✚ Communication (and)
- ✚ Collaborative skills

Fostering creativity in the workplace is said to increase productivity. As Bolan Jones, CEO of PGI (Web-based collaboration software firm) said- *“I believe creativity leads to productivity, provided that the workplace environment is developed and nurtured in a way that allows the two to peacefully co-exist”*. Creative people tend to formulate innovative solutions for the problem or a requirement. There occurs a need to communicate these solutions and collaborate with the team to make the idea work as well. The alternative solutions and possibilities of that problem or requirement requires critical thinking. Therefore, the 4C’s are intertwined and aids an employee in increasing his/her productivity. While it is important to face the challenges with 4C’s, the ability to understand other’s needs, and being aware of their feelings are important. Leadership ability allows employees to help their colleagues improve and excel at their job. Also, empathy encourages trust and relationships which in-turn increases efficiency at the workplace environment. However, the drive to acquire new knowledge is the fundamental of all skills. The rest of the important skills to thrive in the future that refers to the ability to adapt (adaptability), re-skill

according to requirements (agility), attain mutual gain without conflicts (negotiation) and the mind-set to learn from failures (entrepreneurial mind-set) are considered quint essential.

V.CONCLUSION

The “*Study on Reshaping a Future-New World of Work*” provides an analysed report on the major causes (or) forces of the rapid transitions at present, in the workplace, namely

- ✚ Emerging Practices
- ✚ Pandemic
- ✚ Technology (and)
- ✚ Mind-set shift of the employees

The reasons attributed to the strength of these forces was categorised using the Affinity diagram and root-cause analysis of the categorised data was performed using the Fishbone diagram. The objectives to *determine the factors causing changes*, and *definition of the changing workplace* was also interpreted through the Fishbone diagram.

As businesses need to tackle these changes, the skills essential for the sustenance were analysed through qualitative content analysis (compiled from the perspective of researchers, executives, and survey reports of businesses). Furthermore, specific *technical and non-technical skills to progress in the future business environment* was analysed and listed out using Tableau (side-by-side bar chart). The *most crucial skills that are mandatorily required by the employees to retain their current jobs/get employed in the future* are listed out using tree-maps (Tableau). In addition, LinkedIn’s most in-demand skills list from the year 2016-2020 was extracted. The same was analysed using Tableau post which a congruence was found between the present study and LinkedIn’s list. The charted comparison is displayed in the later part of this section.

The summary of the findings derived from the analysis are explained in the below order –

- ✚ **Findings 1** - Changes at workplace (New techniques employed in the HR Practices)
- ✚ **Findings 2** - Most essential futuristic skills (Technical and Non-technical)
[Comparison chart between the outcome of the present study versus LinkedIn’s skills list]

1.1.9 Changes at workplace

The workplace is shifting due to the new techniques that are employed in almost all the HR practices. The Fishbone diagram and the interpretation described in the analysis and findings chapter, contains the application of the changes in detail. A summary of the changes is tabulated below-

Table 0-3 Emerging trends in the HR Practices

HR PRACTICES	CONTEMPORARY TECHNIQUES EMPLOYED
<i>Recruitment</i>	Cyber-vetting (discovering the "internet reputation" of employees by vetting their social media profiles, to gauge the employees’ potential)
	Social media recruiting (posting job vacancy in social media platforms as a snack-able content to attract the active and passive candidates to apply)
<i>Training and Development</i>	E-learning models (E-learning courses and platforms)
	Advanced technologies (Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, Gamification - to recreate the work environment virtually)
<i>Work Culture</i>	Hybrid working (work from office and home with increased flexibility)
	Self-managed teams (Mission-driven autonomous teams)
	Inclusivity and diversity (greater acceptance – increased collaboration)
<i>Employee engagement</i>	Job-crafting (allows employees to change their job-related interactions and tasks to a certain extent, to make it more interesting)
<i>Employee Well-being</i>	Hotlines for employees to express concerns (of those who are stressed and frustrated due to Work-from-home)
<i>Talent Management</i>	Talent sharing (across globe through collaboration with other companies – exchange of talent as per requirements to avoid cost of recruiting a new

	candidate
Decision-making	HR analytics (Data-based insights)
HR functions accessibility	Data lakes (central repository to store all kinds of data, process and perform analytics)
	Cloud platforms (to access software applications, stored in cloud, from any devices)
HR Strategies	Skeletal staffing (Employees safety - minimum number of employees required to perform business operations)
	Social footprint (causing a societal impact for mutual benefit)
	Executive pay-cuts during pandemic (to offset cost-related problems)
	Contingent worker expansion - utilising gig economy (due to remote working, leveraging technology thereby reducing cost)

Source: Self-compiled

1.1.10 Most essential futuristic skills

The present study places a premium on the growing importance of soft skills (**Creativity, collaboration, critical thinking, communication and adaptability**). The hybrid working format requires teams across the globe to collaborate and communicate effectively for increased productivity. The chart represents the fact that the most essential hard skills are technology based. Also, there is an increased demand for the **core digital skills, artificial intelligence, UX design and cloud computing** as majority of the business operations rely on data operations – storage, processing and analytics to obtain well-informed data-based insights. The below figure represents the most essential skills to thrive in the future.

Figure 0-5 Displaying top-10 futuristic skills

Source:

Self-generated using Tableau

LinkedIn’s most in-demand skills were extracted to understand the skill-shifts for 5 years. There occurred a vast difference between the skills required in 2016 compared to the essential skills for the future. The consolidation also depicts that it is the blend of both hard and soft skills that can make an individual successful in his/her career. The proportions depend on the nature of the work.

Figure 0-6 Comparison between Present Study vs LinkedIn’s Skills List

Source: Self-

generated using Tableau

The chart depicts a higher congruence between LinkedIn’s published skills list and the outcome of the present study. This indicates that employers across the globe have developed a similar perspective on the most essential skills to thrive in the future. However, the chart focuses only on the futuristic skills. The detailed compilation of skills in-demand since 2016, has been reported in the previous chapter. This chart is to make the congruence between the present study and LinkedIn’s skills list, more evident.

Suggestions

The greatest concern for the organizations at present is, adjusting to the rapid transformations at the workplace. The organizations are forced to change rapidly, create new initiatives, and train their employees to be more agile to thrive in the transforming business environment. The most difficult part lies in managing these transitions. This is the stage in which the companies learn how to implement conditions needed to reach the desired future state. Hence, the organizations must develop roadmaps for changes to navigate from the current state to desired future.

1.1.11 Transitioning from Current State to Future State

Once the gaps are identified, the strategy imperatives need to be devised rapidly. Also, the initiatives under-taken to close the gap, should be communicated to employees. This is because the sudden transitions will have a considerable impact on the employees’ nature of work and well-being as well. The employers should bear the onus of providing essential resources to the employees that prepares them to face the up-and-coming challenges. Considering the dynamic shifts in the working methods and the

skills required to perform a task, the followings steps can be followed during the execution of the re-skilling initiative -

- ✦ **The “Talent Marketplace Approach”** – Talent marketplace is a platform that allows consumerization of skills to bridge the demand-supply gap in a real-time basis. Talent Marketplace approach allows the managers across the organization to post job vacancies, or any other talent management initiatives under-taken. Talent Marketplace matches the relevant postings with employee’s skills using smart algorithms and AI. Thereby, talent is utilised for the benefit of the company.
- ✦ **Assessing employee capability** – As the talent market ensures the availability of talent across the scope of the organization, the employee’s interests should be re-examined. To activate the workforce around emerging business opportunities, the employees’ passion needs to be aligned with that of the organizational requirements.
- ✦ **Rewards and incentives** – Due to pandemic, the enrolments for the online courses have skyrocketed. There are certain employees who are more involved and proactive in their career related decisions, thereby staying ahead of an average employee by learning new skills through the self-paced courses. The companies can offer rewards and incentives to the self-driven employees to improve the pace of change.
- ✦ **Scheduling the initiatives** – The executives who are accountable for processing the re-skilling initiatives, should post it in the intranet to make it accessible for all the employees across the organization. The same can be published in the daily newsfeeds of the organization. The formalised document with constant updates on the details of enrolments, course duration, trainer, and others should be uploaded for faster processing of the training imperatives, thereby making the transitions easier.
- ✦ **Sustenance** – The changes with respect to the competencies should be communicated to the employees, a framework enlisting the skills to be acquired and the predicted shelf life should be documented as this provides a better clarity on the business requirements.

Tasks are being digitized and automated at a rapid pace, making work more efficient. Due to this widespread phenomenon, the robots have replaced humans adding redundancy to most job roles. Hence, it is mandatory for the companies to train their employees in core technical skills, considering the decreased shelf life of the existing skills. This can help employees to fill the technical gap. However, what cannot be taught externally are the internal values, and behaviours. The major difference between the machines and humans is the attribute of empathy. The employees should develop a drive to know thyself – strengths, weaknesses, threats, and opportunities. This will aid to strengthen qualities that are most essential to face the up-coming future. While the field of data science has acquired importance, there lies a major part of employees - to analyse the data, interpret the findings and apply the results in formulating effective strategy. The importance of human involvement is evident here. Subsequently, when the involvement of humans is essential; then it is only because of the qualities such as critical thinking, problem solving, collaboration, empathy, learning agility and the like – that are very much a part of professional (or) soft skills.

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